

Management

PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL TO ENSURE QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM (QMS)

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Abstract

This study assessed the teaching performance of faculty members in the selected campuses in one of the state universities in the Visayas. It answered the following objectives: describe faculty demographics; contrast the results of the PAR and the SAS used by the university in evaluating the performance of faculty; analyze the relationship between the profile of the faculty and of their performance; ascertain the views of the supervisors and students on the performance of faculty; compare their performance as regards to gender; and extrapolate the problems met by them relative to the nature of their work. This study utilized the descriptive method in the evaluation of faculty performance using the PAR and the SAS. Performance appraisal, as an ISO mechanism for quality, reflected to mirror both positive and negative realities in the workplace. Positive realities like experience and educational qualification of faculty maintain the quality status of the three campuses in the university under study; while negative realities opened more possibilities for benchmarking of the usual operational system of personnel management; this would open greater possibilities for a transitional management and effective delivery system in a state university.

Keywords: Quality; Performance Appraisal Report; Student Assessment Survey; QMS.

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1. Introduction

Quality is a language that embraces humanity's life aspiration to be worth living. The global impact on this regard cannot be overemphasized as human individual puts premium to a better

standard of living, which he or she aspires to establish quality in his or her mundane tasks in the workplace. This global impact is very noble; but there are critical questions on its achievement. How to indulge quality in the organization's diverse cultural practices? Whose standards of quality that can be modelled? How to sustain the culture of quality in the workplace?

To maintain the culture of organizational quality, the institution observes certain standards, which serves as framework to ensure high level of efficiency and effectiveness, as prescribed by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). Experts and trainers of the ISO have collectively advocated for the practice of a culture of quality in the organizational system, not only in the big companies and industries; but also in educational institutions like the universities, where higher learning and advanced studies are provided to stakeholders.

The context in Philippine education system, as what Lapiz concludes that this system is in the process of reconfiguration in responding to inevitable global changes, just like the Philippine integration in the ASEAN and the challenges pose to more responsive curricula from basic education to higher education,^[1] using the Outcomes-based Education (OBE) framework. Importantly the great equalizer to life's enduring pressure and demand is education. It is the subject of scholarly discussion to many experts in the academe. As a great equalizer, it finds solace in the hands of highly competent men and women in the academe whose professionalism is beyond reproach.

Rosaroso, Dakay & Sarmiento emphasize that the global academic environment has gained mobility to drive higher Philippine education institution to shift gear in their services in order to be globally competitive.^[2] Quality Education (QE) is the end product of the effective efforts of quality educators in the academia, who are considered as practicing scholars in their field of science and arts. They are the chief architect in the growth and development of our students who stand tall in producing the very able men and women who meet the challenge and hold the reign of the nation's wheels of progress. Scenarios differ; change is underway; time travels like a fleeting arrow; and the constancy of change has become a new paradigm in the universities, through their vibrant research faculty, who continuously accepts the arduous challenges of research in generating new knowledge to improve quality instruction and quality school management. Teaching approaches, methods, and techniques styles may vary. However, the end in mind is always the production of empowered and satisfied students, who are expected to bring the culture of excellence in the workplace, the nation, and the world.

One of the important phases of the process approach in the Quality Management System (QMS) is the measurement, analysis and evaluation in relation to product realization. Thus, *sine qua non* in the concept of continual improvement is the evaluation of how the teachers deliver the goods. William Glasser, in his Choice Theory of Educational Leadership, puts much premium on people-oriented leadership rather than the use of boss oriented management to maintain the so called "Quality School" with quality school teachers, who are not depersonalized; but maintained a higher degree of self-regulation to chart for better quality and excellence in career life.^[3]

It is imperative, therefore, that the performance of the teachers be evaluated in the light of how their supervisors view it on one hand, and how the students see it on the other hand. Along this line, the Philippine higher education urges the vertical and lateral articulation of specialization of

degrees from the undergraduate to the graduate level of education to ensure quality of higher education degree offerings through outcomes-based and typology-based quality assurance.^[4] It is expected that teacher's self-efficacies are hastened to the fullest once this noble undertaking in higher education in the Philippines will be fully in place.

1.1. Review of Literature

Faculty Demographics

Age, gender, educational attainment, and teaching experience comprised the demographic profiles of faculty in most schools. Though several studies prove that demographic profiles are no longer significant to predict relationships; but this study insists to document these as an essential data for policy formulation and future plan of action by the university system. In terms of age, Inocian & Hermosa rejoin that those ages within the bracket of 30s and 40s "represent the most productive years of career life."^[5] In the graduate tracer study of those who finished Master's Degree in Education, major in Social Studies, it purports that 55 % of the respondents occupy "leadership positions as dean, chairman, principal, coordinator, curator, resident ombudsman, and academic supervisor."^[5]

In a highly gender sensitive society, Borromeo, Prudente & Tayag assert that gender does not anymore predict employment considering other factors such as family and other institutional orientations.^[6] Educational Attainment is pursued among several faculty members, not just for seeking for higher position and better salary; but for continuing professional stewardship.^[5] Rojas & Rojas rejoin that preparation in academics and performance in career life may show importance to obtain success in public school employment.^[7] In terms of teaching experiences, the longer the number of years the members of the faculty stay in the teaching profession, there is a likelihood for teachers to hone their expertise in their fields from novitiate, advance beginning, competent performing, proficient performing, and to being an expert.^[5] This projects the faculty members' rise from the ranks from the first day of employment until the last day of retirement.

Supervisor's Appraisal of the Faculty

One of the provocative and highly interesting topics in educational management is performance appraisal.^[8] As a professor, teaching in the university is a demanding task; members of the faculty in the academia facilitate and achieve the process of teaching in the most excellent way.^[9] Thus, deans or supervisors in the university purport a crucial role in the periodic evaluation of the teaching performance of their faculty. With performance appraisal, Karkoulian rejoins that this "improves universities and thus position higher education institutions at the center of educational excellence."^[8] Teacher performance evaluation is very important in determining teaching excellence (Martinez in Diaz, Borges, Valadez, and Zambrano).^[10] What constitutes the Faculty Appraisal? Most colleges in Qatar have three major components of their faculty appraisal, which includes teaching, scholarly endeavor, and service to the university.^[11]

Student Assessment of Faculty Performance

The students who are the most unexperienced stakeholders to evaluate their professors perceive their teachers as a provider of information and wisdom (Miclea & Opre in Arnăutua & Panc),^[9] even if in some cases their evaluations are ignored by most academics because they actually do not know what other academic activities that they are actually engaging.^[12] Stark and Freishtat rejoin that students' assessment to their teachers reveal their queries of "effectiveness" are unable to reckon the actual instructional efficacy of their teachers in the classroom, unless otherwise they could answer the right questions formulated in the assessment instruments.^[13] Once the university adapts the student assessment instrument, it has to undergo a tedious validation of the instrument and to establish consistency and more reliability, without discounting the facts of the changing instructional delivery landscape and faculty demographics.

Relationship of Faculty Profile and Performance

A good educational practice is an important component of teaching performance, in order to ensure teaching quality and apt learning.^[10] Hassna & Raza concludes that teaching performance and scholarly endeavor like educational attainment and number of years of teaching experiences are not related.^[11] When faculty members use engaging collaboration in the classroom to emphasize critical and creative thinking, students may have higher levels of learning outcomes and evaluate better faculty performance.^[14]

Faculty Performance and Gender

Gander reveals that female faculty members have a significant marginal productivity in academic performance which includes research at liberal arts institutions compared among their male counterparts.^[15] In the study conducted by Rorstad and Aksnes involving more than 12,000 scholars in Norway reveals that positions in academics become more significant compared to gender and age; but when it comes to research, women have published 70 to 80 percent researches compared to men as confirmed by other studies.^[16] This nuances a gap of gender differences in terms of evaluating faculty performance that needs intensive research to make it more gender sensitized.

Problems Met by the Faculty in the Workplace

Sarıçoban has found out five pressing problems met by teachers in Turkey.^[17] Top of the five is the lack of support by the school administration in terms of instructional materials and equipment.^[17] Below of the five is a problem on classroom environment which includes overcrowded classrooms, poor lighting, etc.^[17] Further, he elaborates that problems on course book, students' needs, and teaching strategies emerge second, third, and fourth in the rank.^[17] These problems are commonly seen in most developing and under-developed countries in the world. In the Philippines for instance, there are makeshift classrooms constructed to cater the increasing number of student population which class size increases from 50 to 60 college students in a very limited space in the classroom.

1.2. Research Objectives

The research assessed teaching performance of faculty members in the selected campuses in one of the state universities in the Visayas for Academic Year 2014-2015. It answered the following objectives: describe faculty demographics; contrast the results of the PAR and the SAS used by the university in evaluating the performance of faculty; analyze the relationship between the profile of the faculty and of their performance; ascertain the views of the supervisors and students on the performance of faculty; compare their performance as regards to gender; and extrapolate the problems met by them relative to the nature of their work.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Methodology

The study utilized the descriptive method in quantitative research in the evaluation of the performance of faculty in University X in Central Visayas. A Descriptive Method aimed to provide an accurate description of a situation, through surveys, trend analysis, developmental studies, case studies, and relational studies.^[18] The standard Performance Appraisal Report (PAR) from University X Merit System approved by the Civil Service Commission of the Republic of the Philippines and the Student Assessment Survey (SAS) incorporated into the Quality Policy Manual of University X approved by its Board of Trustees (BOT), as the highest governing board of the university were also used as survey techniques in the study.

2.2. Research Instrument

There were two (3) important standard instruments used in this study, the PAR and the SAS. The PAR or the Performance Appraisal Report used by the Management in evaluating teaching performance and the SAS or the Student Assessment Survey used by the students in assessing teaching performance. The other important instrument was the Survey Form to elicit the problems met by the teachers and students during instruction. These three institutional instruments were standardized based on the requirements of the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), as an international standard used by the University X system wide operation to meet the demands for internationalization.

2.3. Statistical Treatment

The simple percentage and weighted mean were utilized in analyzing the profile of faculty in three selected campus. Teachers' performance was determined using the standard Performance Evaluation Form adopted by University X. Faculty performance as viewed by the students was determined by using the Student Assessment Survey (SAS) Form, an ISO Form used by the University X system. The chi-square test was utilized in determining the relationship between identified profile of teachers and the performance of the teachers as evaluated by the management and by the students. The t-test for mean difference was applied in the determination of the mean difference between the evaluation made by the management and that of the students.

2.4. Research Respondents

A total of 421 faculty members of which 244 were males and 177 were females, who were selected within the three campuses of the 9 campuses of the University X system (Republic Act No. 9744),^[19] using the purposive of non-probability sampling in terms of the number of course offerings, number of faculty, and number of graduates, and performance of the Licensure Examinations of the professional degrees offered as inclusion criteria in the sample. A purposive sampling was utilized to address the target population on the basis of fit and purpose of the study using inclusion and exclusion criteria.^[20]

2.5. Research Environment

There were three research environments in the study. The University X Main Campus, which is located at the heart of the Cebu City. The University X-C campus is located in the northern part; while the University X-A campus is located in the southern part of the main Campus. These three campuses were managed by a campus director under the supervision of the University President in the main campus. They were also selected because of a good track record in the agricultural sector more especially for C and A campuses.

2.6. Research Protocols

A topic defense was made for the approval of the title. After the title was approved a research proposal was presented to the research coordinator and the Research Congress for the approval of the Vice President for Research in the University X, when research funding is needed. A transmittal letter was addressed to the campus director for his or her approval in the gathering and interpretation of data. A separate letter of informed consent was sent to the Dean of the Student Affairs office for the utilization of the PAR and SAS data. Names and the identification of the respondents including the name of the university were withheld to observe confidentiality and ethical considerations of the study.

2.7. Data Gathering Procedure

After all the research protocols were complied, the PAR and the SAS results of the three campuses in Academic Year 2014-2015 were perused and deduced based on the variables required in the study. A specific research assistant took care in the collation of data objectively in each of the three campuses. With the help of a statistician the treatment of data was realized.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Profile of the Faculty Members

3.1.1. Age

As shown in Graph 1, the respondents' average age ranged from 44 to 45 which fairly fell in the middle age bracket, an indication of mature faculty members which would be needed in the academe. These working ages characterized mature roles to teach in the university, with

transcending wisdom to perform the life of a scholar, a researcher, and a performing scientist. The main campus showed the greater bulk of these faculty members to bring the banner of excellence in the university with the collegial support of the faculty in C and A campuses for possible tie and linkage in the University X system. As implied, the young faculty members in the three campuses deserved to be mentored in terms of their diverse roles as professors in the university, in order to carry out the culture of excellence of technology education in the Philippines. As part of monitoring, it was implied that these teachers need a regular monitoring in addressing the gaps in instructional delivery process such as the needed facilities and teaching strategies to improve quality instruction.

Graph 1: Age Profile of the Faculty Members in three Selected Campuses

3.1.2. Gender

Gender of the faculty members as shown in Graph 2 indicated that there were more male faculty members (244) than with females (177) in the three selected campuses under survey. This showed opposite to the general findings in many studies that female teachers outnumbered the male teachers by a mile. This explained by the fact that University X, a technological university, where male faculty members outnumbered the females, and indication of the old notion of gendered segregation in terms of work orientation that males could perform more efficiently in technical and vocation technology compared to women. This finding implied that awareness of Gender and Development (GAD) program of government as provided by law^[19] splintered the entry of women in the technology world as shown among the 177 female faculty members who tried to become co-equaled in terms of professional work opportunity which only men had enjoyed for centuries hence, in a long history of patriarchy in the Philippines. This finding nuanced awareness of a gender-sensitive-leadership in the academe.^[5]

Though, the Philippines ranked 5th in the world as one of the gendered sensitive countries in the world; but an assertion of the feminist movement in the university necessitated a voice to be heard among powerful women who wanted to see their contributions in the fields of arts and sciences, which the Philippines had been deprived decades and centuries ago. Though, the Philippines had produced two female presidents already and a several women political leaders in three branches of government;^[21] but their number was still very few compared to the number of men in these aforementioned sectors.

Graph 2: Gender Profile of the Faculty Members in three Selected Campuses

3.1.3. Educational Attainment

Graph 3: Faculty Members Educational Attainment

Attending in the graduate school for advanced studies in any field of endeavor is a component of a lifelong learning process.^[22] Hence, it is trending in the Philippines to proceed to graduate school to finish another degree in order to get promotion of the present job or the possibility of an increase of the present monthly salary. As shown in Graph 3, a greater than 50% of the faculty finished their master's degree, meeting the minimum educational qualification set by CSC and CHED for their entry in Philippine tertiary education. Added second in the professional qualification is the number of full-pledged doctorate degrees in different fields of specialization. The rest with units in their masters and doctorate degrees implied that the faculty members dreamed for professional growth and development by finishing their advanced studies in line with their area of specialization.^[5] This would show an imperative implication for this number faculty members to proceed and complete their higher education. Lapiz recommended that

pursuing to higher degrees, faculty alignment and policies on typology be strictly observed based on CHED guidelines.^[1]

3.1.4. Teaching Experience

Graph 4 showed the teaching experience of the faculty members in terms of number of years. The average years of teaching experiences indicated between 9 to 16 years. This nuanced a relatively young generation of teachers handling the difficult task in sustaining quality instruction in the university. They were characterized as young, aggressive and mature teachers who were equally responsive to the challenges of the changing time. Though these faculty members exhibited remarkable attributes; but they remained struggling to fully become well-rounded, instinctive, and aware in order to achieve high proficiency in their teaching assignment.^[5]

Graph 4: Teaching Experience

3.2. Distribution of Performance Ratings

3.2.1. Performance Appraisal Rating

The performance of the teachers was evaluated with the use of the PAR used by the university administrators in the evaluation of their teachers' teaching performance. Graph 5 showed that the teachers in the three campuses, under survey, were rated highly by their supervisors, with no teachers rated lower than very satisfactory except for one in the University X Main Campus. This implied that supervisors were kinder to their teachers realizing the present physical condition of the three campuses under study, or protected the general interests of their faculty to stay longer in the university through thick and thin, in exchange of higher performance ratings.

Graph 5: Performance Appraisal Rating Result

3.2.2. Students' Assessment Survey

Graph 6: Student Assessment Survey Result

Students' Assessment showed a generally similar picture with that of the supervisors' assessment. However there were thirty (30) teachers who were rated satisfactory and three (3) teachers rated unsatisfactory. It appeared that the students were more discriminating than that of the supervisors in evaluating teachers. This was attributed by the top three problems met by the faculty in the University X system which the student respondents saw as very critical that affected their evaluation with their teachers. No teacher could prove best in his or her teaching performance in a disturbing physical learning environment characterized with lack of classroom and facilities like laboratories and the like. Teaching strategies along with this problem were also found problematic because side by side with physical facilities which were badly challenged. How could a technology teacher dispense the best for his or her craft if the needed facilities were not sufficient enough for the number of enrolled students? This inquisitive argument necessitated

a more nuanced understanding of University X stakeholders to respond and protect the integrity of the university.

3.3. Faculty Demographics and of Teaching Performance

3.3.1. Educational Attainment and Performance Rating

Table 1 showed the relationship between the teachers’ educational attainment and their performance rating. The computed T-value of 0.037 which when compared to the Table Value of 11.071 is evidently less, which meant that there was no significant relationship between educational attainment and the performance rating, which led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implied that educational attainment would not affect the performance rating of the faculty—an indication showed that to be an effective teacher in the classroom is not measured by the number of advanced studies earned in the university. This finding was confirmed in the study of Hassna & Raza that teaching performance is unrelated to scholarly endeavor or educational attainment. ^[11] A classic exclusionism principle that competence in teaching, i.e. associated with the arts to teach would not be measured by the rigors of intellectualization in the science of teaching, which relatively achieved through the numbers of training, seminar, workshop and completion of the degrees in advanced studies. These would be necessary to enhance the profession; but not a guarantee to be more competent in the arts of teaching.

Table 1: Correlation between Educational Attainment and Performance Rating

E.Q. PR	Computed T-Value	Table Value at .05	Remarks	Decision
CTU	0.037	11.071	Not Significant	Accept Ho

3.3.2. Years of Teaching Experience and Performance Rating

As shown in Table 2, an insignificant correlation between years of teaching experience and performance rating. It implied that the number of years accumulated would not guarantee for a good teaching performance, which led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This remained consistent with educational attainment; the number of years of teaching experience would not affect whether or not the teacher’s competency to teach more efficiently and effectively in the classroom. This validated that seniority would not matter as a parameter for better teaching performance, because they could have possessed the wisdom gained in the number of years of teaching experience; but they would not have touched the lives of their students in bringing out the lesson to their real life experiences, then this would affect their low performance. “Teaching is not overshadowed by too much acquisition and transmission of knowledge; but with a personal inclination that touches the human psyche of our experiences.” It also implied that evaluation of teachers was conducted periodically; but there showed no indication of monitoring, follow-up, and discussion with the teachers regarding their evaluation results.

Table 2: Correlation between No. of Years in Teaching and Performance Rating

E.Q. PR	Computed T-Value	Table Value at .05	Remarks	Decision
CTU	0.310	9.488	Not Significant	Accept Ho

3.4. Teachers' Performance as Viewed by the Supervisors and Students

Table 3 showed the data on the Mean Difference of Performance of the teachers as rated by the supervisors and students. The t-value was less than the table-value at .05 level of significance. This indicated that there was no significant mean difference of the performance rating done by the supervisors and the students to the faculty, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The similar views between the supervisors and students regarding teachers' performance were insignificant attributed by these factors such as: contentment of the status quo, depersonalization and indifference, and incompetent leadership. The raters would think that the performance of these teachers had no difference from the previous years, which would contribute to a high level of teacher indifference. Some teachers would also think that their performance did not improve, which was attributed by laxity or inadequacy of some of their immediate supervisors in terms of their leadership and management styles in monitoring their quality of teaching, and the failure to give them enough recognition. Blackburn & Clark rejoined that most teachers honestly believed they would perform at the higher levels of their job when they received both personal and institutional recognition.^[12] Awards and recognition mattered to ensure better teaching performance in the instructional delivery and other university related activities. Support and reward system extended by the administration to the faculty would play a critical component of college students' learning experiences.^[14]

Table 3: Mean Difference between the Ratings of the Supervisors and the Students

Supervisors / Students	Computed T-Value	Table Value .05 level	Remarks	Decision
CTU	-92.59	1.97	Not Significant	Accept Ho

3.5. Teaching Performance of the Male Teachers Compared to the Female Teachers'

Table 4 showed the data of the performance rating of the male teachers compared to that of the female teachers' performance rating. Thus, it showed an insignificant mean among male/female teachers' performance. The higher mean of male teachers than the female teachers nuanced that male teachers in a technological university showed a high authority figure compared than females. Their voices implied to have firm decisions, very direct and practical in their teaching compared to female teachers who exhibited tendencies to be more rhetorical, chatty, and emotional in the classroom. This finding proved Gander's finding in 1999 that female teachers showed excellence on their teaching performance at the liberal arts institutions.^[15]

Table 4: Mean Difference between the Male and the Female Teachers' Teaching Performance

Male / Female	Computed T-Value	Table Value .05 level	Remarks	Decision
CTU	2.25	1.97	Significant	Rejected Ho

3.6. Common Problems Met

Graph 7: Problems Met

The responses on the problems affecting instructional delivery could be viewed in Graph 7. The most pressing concern as perceived by the respondents was the lack of classrooms among the 32% of the total respondents. The inadequacy of classrooms was attributed by the quantum leap in enrolment caused by factors of University X's good image and performance in technology education, proximity, low and affordable tuition fee as one of the country's state colleges and universities. Lack of facilities would also be the result of the unprecedented increase of enrolment and damages brought by torrential typhoons and earthquake that hit the Philippines. There were 26% who viewed it as a major concern. Poor teaching strategies as third viewed among 10% of the total respondents affected quality instruction. The rest of the problems constituting 30% ranged from inadequacy of instructional materials, undisciplined students, lack of cooperation, poor teaching system, sanitation, conflict of schedule, poor laboratory, and lack of supervision. These findings confirmed the study of Sariçoban.^[17]

4. Conclusions & Recommendations

The diverse demographics of faculty among the three campus of University X system proved to have no significant relationship in terms of their teaching performance, except for gender with a significant mean difference attributed by the greater number of male faculty members in the sample population. The no correlation between educational attainment and performance rating; no correlation between number of years teaching experience and their performance rating; and the no difference between the ratings of the supervisors and the students were attributed to a lot challenges in the work environment like: lack of classrooms, inadequate facilities and inadequate instructional materials; and poor teaching strategies. The middle age category of faculty members who were relatively vibrant could protect the integrity of the university who were generally qualified to teach despite problems of physical learning environment. Based on these

conclusions, the following recommendations are offered to respond the study's weak findings. The University X administration will review the existing guidelines on typology of professional qualifications of their faculty, under CHED Memorandum Order No. 46, series of 2012, to reassign them to a specific department where they can give their best in line of their area of specialization from the undergraduate to the graduate level and find effective measures like scholarship to let them go back to the university again to study and become vertically articulated. Consider the five year development plan of the physical plant of the three campuses to look for a remedy in restructuring the damaged facilities and the lack of its kind. Find avenues for possible bench-marking of teaching practices and seminars and trainings to improve the quality of College instruction vis-à-vis maintaining the balance policies required by the International Organization for Standardization.

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